

THE ROLE OF VOVINAM IN THE LIFE OF VIETNAMESE PEOPLE

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Abstract:

Vovinam – Viet Vo Dao (Vovinam) is a Vietnamese martial art which is considered one of the useful means for training self-defense and fighting skills, raising spirit and educating learners' morality and personality. Vovinam is a creative combination of many different domestic and foreign martial arts aiming at selecting techniques and strikes to diversify exercises system and program contents. Vovinam techniques are incorporated easily creating excitement and interest for learners especially the young generation.

Keywords: Vovinam; martial art; martial art philosophy; fair-play spirit; Vovinam technique system;

1. Introduction

Martial arts in general or Vovinam in particular is regarded as one of the effective methods to train morality, spirit, will, health, self-defense, combat skills of all people, of the army not only in the war time but also in the peace.

In comparison with some traditional martial arts of Vietnamese people having existed for a long time such as traditional martial art, Vietnamese wrestling, and with some adopted from foreign countries like Kung Fu of Chinese, Karate, Judo and Aikido of Japanese, Taekwondo of Korean, etc., Vovinam has formed and developed much later. However, the birth of Vovinam has encouraged the development of other martial arts, enriched the world's martial arts and contributed to:

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“...tempering and donating for the nation excellent people who have virtue, indomitable will, enough competence and health to overcome difficulties and challenges, to defeat the weakness, feebleness in soul and body in order to reach a better lifestyle: Live to help others live and live for others”

(Le Quoc An, 2008)

2. Content

2.1. Introduction of Vovinam

Vovinam was found by the late grandmaster Nguyen Loc in 1936 in the north of Vietnam, but practiced secretly. In 1938, he publicized it and at the same time set forth his theory “body and mind revolution” to encourage practitioners to reform themselves and incline both body and mind to the good

Vovinam is a clever, harmonious and skillful combination of the essence of different martial arts in Vietnam as well as in the world such as traditional Vietnamese wrestling, traditional Vietnamese martial art, Chinese Kung Fu. This combination ensures the suitability for each learner’s physical state, the diversity of content and techniques. Based on the principle of “*hard and soft combination in performance*”, Vovinam practitioners are trained with strikes using bare hand, elbow, leg, knee and strikes with weapons like sword, broadsword, machete, knife, staff, fan... Besides, they also learn how to cope with armed opponents by bare hand, how to launch counter-attacks, unlock and wrestle.

Despite of appearing later than other martial arts, Vovinam, nowadays, has obtained a large-scale development with followers in more than sixty countries in the world including Cambodia, Thailand, Singapore, Belgium, Poland, Denmark, Switzerland, Sweden, Italy, Australia, India, Iran etc. Many national and continental Vovinam federations have been established in countries having Vovinam practitioners as Spain, Italy, America, Algeria etc. After the World Vovinam-VietVoDao Federation was formed in 2008 in Vietnam, continental Vovinam federations have been born accordingly: Congresses were organized to establish the European Vovinam-VietVoDao Federation (EVVF) in Paris on October 16th, 2010; The South East Asian Vovinam Federation (SEAVF) in Cambodia on December 28th, 2010; The African Vovinam Federation (AFVF) in Algeria on January 11, 2012. In 2011, Vovinam was first introduced into the official competition program in the 26th SEA Games (The 26th South East Asian Games).

Thanks to those having enthusiasm, strategic vision, and the love for Vovinam, they orient goals for developing and advertising Vovinam to friends all over the globe.

2.2 The Role of Vovinam

It could be said that martial arts play an important role and gain a vital position in the early stage of the construction and defense of each nation's territory and people. In this period, that science and technology have not been developed, fighting weapons have been fairly simple, there have been no clear rules, human's awareness has remained limitation, man's heart has not been connected together cause hidden conflicts among people waiting for a chance to erupt, disrupt and kill each other. Therefore, they have always kept conscious of the existence, the protection of their own territory. In order to save themselves and their countries, the best way is practicing combat skills, training hand and leg techniques making them strong and techniques with simple weapons (stick, knife, sword, bow and arrow, etc.) to settle down struggles in life, keep their sovereignty over the country. From the fighting reality, they have gained much practical experiences, thence ceaselessly studied to create more new techniques making it far more diversified and useful. Martial arts in this time could be seen as a key factor in the process of building and defending the national territory. Even some countries have sent in their troops to invade, occupy and take over others. Hence, families and dynasties in this period have mainly concentrated on practicing martial arts to resolve political conflicts. Obviously, martial arts have a great influence on political activities. It seems that all leaders of a country stay skillful in martial arts.

When the growth of human society has maintained restrictions together with vague regulations, people have existed in the belief "*win for the strong, failure for the weak*". For this reason, they have considered physical strength and high level of martial arts skill as fundamental elements for seizing power, appropriating benefits, tyrannizing the weak. Because of the essential need for continuity of their lives, people have become aware of martial arts training (poor peasants, slaves and the weak practice martial arts to become strong and able to protect themselves. The rich, landowners and the state organizations do the same on one hand to save their property and territory and on the other hand to transgress land, gain power, and invade other countries...)

In these days, the considerable development of science, the improvement and civilization of human society and the clarity of the law make the nature of martial arts changed (its nature is fighting). The idea of martial arts nowadays does not purely refer to the practice of fighting skills, the use of arm and leg to settle conflicts, the show of muscular strength over the weak, but additionally mentions health enhancement, physical development, will and spirit training and many great philosophies in life. For the place where martial arts skills are practiced is seen not only a martial arts school but also a school of moral standards. Practicing martial arts is for the purpose of preserving the tradition of teacher deference and moral respect, principles, disciplines and rules, all of which are difficult to retain at many sport stadiums or even in schools today. More

importantly, martial arts do not end with the function of health improvement; conversely always try to reach a higher goal - "*martial arts philosophy*"- helping practitioners perfect their qualities, morality and lifestyle. Therefore, up to the present time almost every country on earth has created a typical martial art suitable for cultural characters and physical condition of its own nation. Moreover, due to the need for exchange and integration in the fields of economy, culture, politics, sport, etc., lots of countries have opened their door to welcome different martial arts into their territory, resulting in the variety and diversity of the world's martial arts.

Particularly, Vietnamese Vovinam also has its own features but suits the general development trend of the global sport, thus it is practiced worldwide. The principle of Vovinam outlines that teaching people martial art techniques, then guiding them what to do to get advantages for themselves and others is martial arts philosophy. If someone already has their own principles and learns martial arts afterwards to protect and promote those principles, which means martial arts are used as a means or a tool, not "*martial arts philosophy*". Vovinam follows the independent and pure philosophy, consistently refuses all distractions or synchronization of religion and politics. Hence, Vovinam is growing to become the martial art philosophy of martial arts philosophies, which means the philosophy of Vovinam is the purest of humans. The spirit of the philosophy is shown in one's lifestyle, affection, behaviors towards others from which all people understand and express their respect to that person before perceiving the philosophy. Good impression about a real philosophical spirit without national borders or barriers between classes, religions touches his senses. Finally, the pre-eminent humanity value of Vovinam is manifested in the benevolence, combination, magnanimity, and equality with everyone as well as in the fairness of races, religions and parties.

2.3. Discussion

2.3.1 The Role of Vovinam towards Life

It is possible to see that Vietnamese martial art is a valuable part of the national culture. From the time it was born, formed, until developed, it has always accompanied the fights, the constructions and the defenses of the country. It displays the private spirits and characters of the nation having gone through thousands of years dominated.

In the new age, those taking part in martial art training are no longer to drive away invaders or to oppress the weak who have no family or support, but with the aim of improving health, mind, will, protecting themselves and assisting people in danger. They are especially taught "*virtues*" in martial art philosophy and the word "*tolerance*" in martial art principles, both of which are considered to be life value, high spirit, fair

play spirit, teacher deference, moral respect and moral qualities of human. The learners have always been reminded and explained by their masters about the origin *“Gratitude is the sign of noble souls”*, *“When you eat a fruit, think of the man who planted the tree”*, about personality. This is one of outstanding qualities of Vietnamese people in general as well as of Vovinam philosophy in particular.

Together with the rapid growth of society, the acceptance and interrelation among many different cultures from many different countries require the martial art members to obey and seriously perform regulations, internal rules of the school in order to show being an educated person with standards of morality and philosophical spirit. Vovinam philosophy has been accumulated and enhanced greatly about its values and meaning in humankind’s present life. It is one of the factors building the happy spiritual life for all those who love and participate in this martial art all over the world.

Contributions of Vovinam in educating righteousness. *“It is claimed that “righteousness” is one of moral categories having popular meaning in the cultural and spiritual life”* (Vo Van Dung, 2011) in Eastern countries in general and in Vietnam in particular. With the cultural typicality and the tradition of *“teacher deference, moral respect”* of Vietnamese people, *“righteousness”* is always put to the top. It is a model, a measurement in all social communication, thus each of Vietnamese people has responsibility to learn and improve themselves. Study of righteousness is more important and necessary than that of literature, that explains why there is always a big motto: *“Study manners first and then learn to read and write”* hung above the main gates or in classrooms of all schools from primary to high ones in Vietnam. Righteousness is taught at the very first stage to orient students towards respect for the elder, kindness to the young, politeness to parents, teachers, surrounding people and acceptable behavior. To martial art practitioners, *“righteousness”* is a firm and unifying content trained constantly in the whole process of teaching and learning the martial art. As righteousness is considered as one of friendly ways helping people self-improve their soul and characters, be mindful of moral principles, and gradually enhance and perfect personal qualities, mind and determination.

The present development, integration, cultural exchange among countries in the world together with the fast growth of information, media system and other aspects of society have generated positive sides along with negative ones. If everybody is not steady in their mind accepting those changes without serious consideration, they will be melted into a whirl of ill culture making traditional values of each nation easy to be corrupted, distorted and making human’s morality spoiled. The present circumstance demonstrates the fact that only martial art still maintains the tradition of *“teacher deference, moral respect”*, esteeming and keeping righteousness. For those come to the club which is not simply a place for practicing martial art techniques, enhancing health,

training fighting skills as some people think, but a martial art school, a morality school and a place for educating moral principles, personality and way of life...The first lesson for martial art learners is righteousness (righteousness of martial art, righteousness of social life), respecting teachers and other practitioners. In martial art school, based on many tests learners are assessed according to two criteria including martial art achievements and moral quality through their behavior and relation with other people.

Therefore, it is very important for Vovinam novices to fulfill one of the first criteria that requires much time and patience. Such the criterion comprises acquiring righteousness and ways of behaving, communicating, moving, addressing, etc.. Righteousness is regarded as a compulsory and essential content starting the study of martial art and being impossible to be underestimated or ignored.

Discussing about the aspect of "*Salutation*" in Vovinam, the founder of the school asserted that the salutation "*iron hand over benevolent heart*" is to begin all communicative activities in meetings, before ceremonies, before and after performances or competitions. The symbol of power is the iron hand. The benevolent heart symbolizes affection. The iron hand is formed by regular practice. The generous heart is shaped by the comprehension of martial art philosophy.

When putting the hand over the heart for "*Salutation*", Vovinam followers always notice that martial art is only used with love. This means the iron hand must accompany the benevolent heart: Bravery must be together with kindness; Martial art skills must go with martial art philosophy. The martial art is employed to warn, emotionalize and encourage others, not to punish or force obedience from others

Salutation is the first lesson for all Vovinam members. This lesson is a precious and useful experience, a manual including not only a wide range of martial art skills but also affection and virtues that every Vovinam member needs to possess. The lesson surely leads Vovinam learners to the supports of Vovinam that are love, forgiveness and purification.

Body bends down to express the respect with the whole heart. Face slightly rises up to show the righteousness and probity. The movements remain gentle, flexible and clever but reflect the proud and firm attitude of a real person. Raising face to look at the opposite with tolerant cheerful eyes proves their formality, purity, and straightforwardness.

Hence, virtue is cultivated every time when there is a performance of "*Salutation*". Each strike assists Vovinam practitioners to express their virtue and the love for Vovinam closely and sociably. No one can refuse the obvious truth that:

"...the rite of Salutation is an absolute symbol of the unity in heart and spirit with high self-consciousness and voluntariness of Vovinam members"

(Nguyen Duc Quynh Ky, 2011)

Contributions of Vovinam in educating moral qualities. According to Eastern martial art philosophy in general as well as Vovinam's in particular, when talking about principles in martial art, the founders and masters usually refer to principles for being a human, a responsible life to oneself and society and the truths, all of which direct the martial art learners to a better and more useful life for society. The learners always consider moral qualities to be their foundation

Therefore, *"martial art principles"* have a wide philosophical meaning about the martial art: planning tendencies and methods of practicing and training learners' body and mind; forming tolerability, patience and strong competence to overcome difficulties, win themselves, obey regulations in community, balance their daily life, control behavior and solve problems brightly. Vovinam members do not express high self-evaluation, self-content and oppression of the weak. *"Bravery accompanies affection; Martial art skills go with martial art philosophy; Martial art practitioners only use martial art when love is embedded in every strike"*

To history, martial art has accompanied combats from the time it was born. However, it is not for that reason the practitioners only know fighting or hand and leg strikes. The martial art contains in it a lofty philosophy, a tolerant heart and even a high-minded person. The purpose of learning martial art is comprehensively developing oneself in both physical and mental state, directing people to the rightness, the truth, kindness, doing the good and avoiding the bad and leading learners to the beauty of the soul and body *"truth – goodness - beauty"*. Martial art philosophy exists in martial art. The followers have to defeat obstacles and challenges from outside, and more importantly win their own desires. Precious qualities will be built up throughout the training such as endurance, tolerability, quickness, wisdom, bravery etc.. The learners are expected to possess great qualities like modesty, patience, simplicity, tolerance and kindness.

Martial art masters often teach that the practice of the martial art aims at improving health, protecting ourselves and the weak; Martial art learners live for the right and avoid ignoring the wrong. Thus, it is necessary for the learners to acquire how to use the martial art, which means that they are not allowed to employ it for black purposes like threatening, harming or pushing other people to death. Kindness and deference, modesty and humbleness, bravery and belief, standards of communicative behavior are noble philosophy of human accumulated and formed during the process of learning the martial art.

In the age of development and integration among most of the countries in the world as the present time, the healthy lifestyle as well as the morality of a group of young people tends to decline seriously. Social evils and school violence are happening everywhere. Modesty, humbleness, kindness and communicative behavior are no longer standard. Hence, in my opinion, regardless of education in school, family and society, it is only martial art to educate morality well for martial art learners in general and the young generation in particular. "*Martial art philosophy*" of Vovinam is shown in ten thoughtful principles according to the newest program composed by the patriarch Nguyen Van Chieu and publicized since 2009. It is compulsory for Vovinam practitioners to remember that (1) Vovinam martial art practitioners vow to pursue the high level of art to serve the nation and humankind; (2) Vovinam martial art practitioners vow to be faithful to the intentions, to develop the school and to guide the young generations to devote themselves for the good (3) Vovinam martial art practitioners are consistently united in heart and spirit, respectful of the elder and kind to peers; (4) Vovinam martial art practitioners absolutely keep regulations, highly raise their honor; (5) Vovinam martial art practitioners respect other martial art schools and only utilize the martial art to self-defend and serve the justice; (6) Vovinam martial art practitioners are diligent in study, spirit training and moral enhancement; (7) Vovinam martial art practitioners live their life healthily, simply, faithfully, and nobly; (8) Vovinam martial art practitioners retain a strong will, attempt to improve themselves; (9) Vovinam martial art practitioners make thoughtful judgments, steadily struggle with perseverance and cleverly give actions; (10) Vovinam martial art practitioners are always self-confident, modest, generous, self-controlled to get progress.

Educating the fair-play spirit: The fair-play spirit of each nation is the combination of patriotic tradition, bravery, undauntedness in the wars against enemies, diligence in work, unity in combats. This spirit is formed step by step and is considered to be the pride of each nation. In the field of sociology, fair-play spirit is explained to be the high appreciation of martial art skills and martial art philosophy. The martial art users do not attack defeated people, push others to death, use strength to oppress the weak, and take advantage of the crowd to brutalize small groups

Fair play: It is the veneration and the prominence of martial art, the love for refined and noble behavior of martial art community, etc.. The function of martial art is "fighting". The "*veneration*" and "*prominence*" of martial art do not mean revering fighting or belligerence, but relate to the respect for good traditional moral values which are available in the martial art itself or achievable through the process of martial art training. The manifestation of fair-play lies in daily communicative behavior and attitudes such as respecting teachers and the elder, tolerating the young, behaving friendly with fellows, showing affection to others, sharing and helping each other in

study, sickness or difficulties. According to Tran Long, the fair-play spirit of the nation is shown through such the factors as no presumption with success, no bore with failure, no attack on defeated people, a glory for players and a useful life for ourselves and others. (Tran Long, 2013).

In short, martial art learners' fair-play spirit is the reverence of noble qualities, well-educated actions, justice, civilization, and kind behavior towards people.

2.3.2 Contributions of Vovinam in developing physical strength

Martial art in general as well as Vovinam in particular possesses its own attraction causing great curiosity and enquiry for people especially the young generation. For it meets and satisfies the demand for physical training, self-defense and attack on the opponent. Especially, it creates such a standard personality, a resolute spirit and a strong will for its practitioners that other sports find it difficult to do the same. Moreover, the content of Vovinam performance proves a great aesthetic as well as its own characteristics, but stays easy for its members to practice. Therefore, Vovinam has conquered the senses of most people of all classes and careers inside and outside the country.

Nowadays, Vovinam is recognized as a sport attracting lots of people to participate. Like several other physical sports, regular practice of Vovinam positively influences the physiological function, the circulatory system, the respiratory system, the nervous system, muscular system and the development of general physical features such as quickness, strength, endurance, flexibility, cleverness, etc.

Quickness: The repetition of martial art movements will turn into reflex produced with high speed, which is especially suitable for happening incidents, timely and accurate as expected. It also generates working competence of muscles, reactive capacity and responses to stimulations to the nervous system in the shortest time. In addition, supplementary exercises need noticing to promote conditioned reflex, automatic reflex.

Strength: In Vovinam training and competition, strength is shown through force when a strike is delivered. Such the strikes as punches, kicks, etc. have a significant force clearly expressing the strong power. The force is risen from dantian, then spread out to hands and legs by combined elements and important decisions in using inner force.

Endurance: The normal duration of a Vovinam class is from two to three hours during which learners practice with high intensity making the body produce an adaptation for strenuous exercises. It helps maintain muscular energy and biochemical states of the body. The initial force will increase parallel to practice time. The endurance

in Vovinam is accessed by the ability to maintain the respiratory, circulatory and muscular system.

The cleverness and flexibility: They are the result of synchronous combination of complicated and sophisticated movements. They reveal the competence of difficult techniques accomplishment, the strenuous practice and the nervous control. The flexibility as well as the artistic movements is achievable depending on the ability to open joints at wide amplitude in the whole body.

In term of mental power: By means of practicing techniques and analyzing circumstances in real competitions, learners gradually obtain the competence and experience in predicting, analyzing, and dealing with happening incidents most effectively. They are able to foresee what will happen or even their opponents' desires and have proper strategies afterwards.

It is considered that when a person takes part in Vovinam practice, he has to use hands, legs to perform such strikes as punching, kicking, moving, dodging, etc., which is called "physical activities". The use of mind to get knowledge of how to carry out such the strikes most accurately without taking much energy, especially limiting damages to the utmost, is "*mental power*". Therefore, perpetual practice of Vovinam helps foster the learners' working competence in both physicality and mentality.

2.3.3 Contributions of Vovinam in other aspects

The practicality: It is not similar to general training features of other martial arts that learners spend time on stances, katas first and analysis later. Vovinam novices learn techniques preventing being locked (when being grabbed, choked, hugged, etc.), basic counter attacks (when being punched, kicked..) along with blocks, punches, kicks, knee and elbow strikes and falling techniques in the first classes. This is the founder's new idea with the aim of assisting trainees to be able to effectively cope with situations forcing them to self-defend. The practicality is not only relevant to the social settings at that time but also more and more reasonable and valuable nowadays. It is because martial art trainees can on one hand participate in martial art practice, and on the other hand has other essential demands and duties in life as study, art, vocation, entertainment, living, etc.

The continuation: The continuation in Vovinam means a strike delivered always includes a combination of at least three movements. In order to give a counter attack in response to a straight punch from the opponent's right hand, for instance, a Vovinam trainee will simultaneously move his left leg to the left and use his right hand to block the opponent's hand. Then he responds by using the left hand to cut the opponent's face or eyes and ends with a straight punch from the right hand to the belly; or the first attack combination (an interrupted attack) consists of a cut to the eyes or face with a

hand facing down, a low punch to the belly from the right hand in addition, a step forward from the right leg and an elbow strike to the opponent's temple (Qu bin). Generally speaking, it could be a sequence of hand strikes (cut, punch, hook punch, back punch, elbow strike, etc.) or leg ones (kick, side kick, roundhouse kick, hook kick, back kick, etc.), or a mixture of hand and leg strikes (cut and low roundhouse kick, wrestling..). The delivery of such the attack combinations serves the purpose of gaining advantage in self-defense and combat. It especially suits the neat and quick state of Vietnamese people. Besides, it is also prevention in case one or two of the strikes in the sequence is not accurate and effective.

The principle of hard and soft combination in performance: This principle is shown when being attacked, martial art practitioners often avoid strikes first (soft) and give responses later (hard). Vovinam techniques comprise many attack strategies but still ensure this principle. When a kick or a counter attack (hard), for example, is delivered to opponent's body, Vovinam practitioners always use hands to protect their face and genitals (soft). In falling techniques (no danger, no pain), the practitioners have to flex their muscles and curl up (hard), then roll over as landing on the ground (soft) to relieve the opponent's attack force and the falling force of their body. Thanks to the principle, Vovinam practitioners perform strikes or falls on the brick ground as safely as on tatami

In other words, Vovinam techniques system consists of both gentle and strong strikes. Even in every single blow, there is also a hard and soft combination like the balance of Yin and Yang in nature and society. This combination is not simply an implication of softness and hardness, but the flexibility and changeability. Sometimes there is more softness and less hardness or vice versa, and sometimes there is half softness and half hardness depending on each particular situation. Especially, this principle also helps reinforce the learners' spirit life as well as their daily behavior because *"...hardness symbolizes strength, iron will, determination and bravery. Softness signifies gentleness and kindness. It is impossible to have adjustment and flexibility in every situation if there is a lack of softness. Conversely, practitioners find it difficult to boost the effectiveness to the utmost"*

The ability to apply scientific principles into Vovinam techniques: Like many other martial arts, scientific principles are also applied into Vovinam techniques such as the centrifugal force (turning, blocking, parrying, punching or elbow striking given in the arched or circular shape); the force of lever (folding, locking, hooking, blocking...), whirling force (straight punches..), the bending and bouncing force (throwing, striking down, wrestling, jumping...). These scientific principles help learners save their energy in training as well as in performance but gain high effectiveness.

Especially, sweeping cuts, off-balanced cuts, off-balanced elbow strikes (strikes from hand and leg given at the same time in the reverse direction), takedown (strikes from hand and leg given at the same time in the same direction), and flying kicks, pushing kicks, scissor kicks (suddenly delivered as the opponent is careless and unsteady) in the basic leg attacks system used to make the opponent fall are an important technical characteristic of Vovinam

The principle of “one developed to three”: The practicality in the techniques system, in single basic strike or unblock etc. is a crucial training program. However, in order to establish a more advantageous condition for the practitioners to skillfully practice basic strikes and accordingly cope with different circumstances, Vovinam techniques system includes two different training methods including (1) single form (bare hand katas, weapon katas) and (2) dual form (two practitioners perform some basic techniques like unblocks or strikes with weapons) which are combined properly. From the root of basic strikes and unblocks, learners develop them to single form and dual form. Group form is the principle of “one developed to three” in Vovinam techniques system.

For the last two decades, Vovinam enriches its system by adding several exercises training breathing skill for all practitioners and uninterrupted dual forms including gentle movements without falling strikes for the old people. Despite of the constant build-up of attack system with bare hands and weapons (knife, sword, axe, machete, ruler, broadsword, etc.) for more than forty years, Vovinam still ensures the initial basic features as well as express characteristics of tradition and modernity of Vietnamese people.

Typical features of Vovinam in comparison with other martial arts: Vovinam has both modern and traditional characteristics which are expressed by the use of simple techniques associated with scientific principles. These techniques aid learners to successfully practice simple or complicated strikes such as attacks given in different directions (linear or circular..), single or combined attacks.

Vovinam focuses on the combination of body's parts used as a weapon for self-defense or attack such as hand sides, elbows, knees, legs. Vovinam also pays attention to the practicality. It has many dangerous strikes with fingertips (using fingertips to hit to pressure points) or elbows (elbow strikes are normally very strong for they use powerful muscles from arm and back). Vovinam leg attacks are usually tied up closely with hand. Therefore, it is not easy for the opponent to avoid attacks from Vovinam learners or give counter attacks.

3. Conclusion

From the beneficial and practical values along with technical features like being easy to practice, easy to apply, Vovinam has been developed worldwide. It has attracted lots of people from many different countries to join the practice. It meets the demand of all classes of people in the world for training themselves and helps raise values of life, values of humanity to a higher position. For those who learn this martial art will be conscious of the fact that martial art refers to moral philosophy first, then come techniques. It means that a martial art trainee is initially taught how to be a human, how to live morally, how to become a person with strong will and determination, then martial art techniques and skills to use those techniques.

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